

Is Virtual Fitting Room Technology the vaccine to overcome the COVID-19 Virus in Retail?

**Cas
Bongers**

c.s.bongers@tilbur
guniversity.edu

**Jules
Cox**

j.n.p.cox@tilburgu
niversity.edu

**Laura
van Mil**

l.h.c.vanmil@tilbur
guniversity.edu

**Pieter
Nijsten**

p.f.b.nijsten@tilbur
guniversity.edu

**Elena
Papanikolaou**

e.papanikolaou@til
burguniversity.edu

ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused many disruptions in the business world, to which businesses have to adapt. Retailers all over the world have reacted differently to this crisis. This paper provides examples on how retailers can handle this unprecedented situation through adidas' actions and strategies. Under the circumstances adidas' IT governance has shifted to a business-oriented pattern that has given priority to technological advance. The primary focus of this paper is the implementation of the VFR technology that adidas is experimenting with in terms of a different aspect of supply chain management. Adidas' objective is for the VFR to reduce the costs of returns that always has been a major concern of the retailers. Nevertheless, the VFR application is proven to have a lot of hidden dangers, both on the cybersecurity and the business front, but with attention-to-detail and resilient management, existing mitigation methods can overcome the obstacles.

Keywords

COVID-19, retail and consumer goods, digital transformation, cybersecurity, Virtual Fitting Room

INTRODUCTION

“The COVID-19 pandemic is fuelling the growth of the stay-at-home economy. How consumers learn, work, shop, and play is poised to change forever” (Ingilizian, 2020). Within the apparel, footwear, and accessories industry, a study of Accenture (2020) has revealed that the proportion of purchases made online by infrequent e-commerce users will increase by 100% this year due to the COVID-19 crisis as they got used to online shopping behaviour during lockdowns. Two challenges, however, arise for retailers utilizing their e-commerce strategy. First, as the supply of online products are enormous and 83% of the consumers agree upon the fact that the convenience of online

shopping has become more important than 5 years ago, brands have to look for an online infrastructure that provides them with a competitive advantage (Smart insights, 2020). Second, a solution should be created for one of the biggest problems of online shopping: returns (Hjort and Lantz, 2016). Based on two large-scale field experiments, Yang and Xiong (2019) have concluded that Virtual Fitting Rooms (VFR) can both stimulate convenience with online shopping and reduce returns. In times of the COVID-19 pandemic, the additional benefits of VFR technology became clear as it made it easier for customers to get fitted from home and the risk of exposure to COVID-19 was lowered (Business Insider US, 2020). Although VFR technology is already commonly used in the beauty industry, sports fashion retailers like adidas recently decided to incorporate these technologies as well. Privacy experts, however, warn retailers that VFR technology could also expose biometric and valuable personal data (Bhattarai, 2020). Therefore, more research is needed on how apparel retailers can effectively adopt VFR technology to increase sales and decrease returns.

This research paper aims to study how the Virtual Fitting Room technology may be a valuable add-on and how this could effectively be implemented in the retail sector. First, the paper will investigate how IT governance is changing due to a pandemic like COVID-19 and how this is affecting the decision-making on new IT technologies. Secondly, this paper will conduct a BPI-related COVID-19 analysis and discuss the effects of the implementation of the VFR-technology in the current value chain. Thirdly, this paper aims to investigate the digital risks associated with the VFR-technology, the business risks related to online shopping, and how companies should countermeasure these risks with resilient strategies. Lastly, in addition to the predetermined analyses, research is done on how consumers will adopt and perceive a new technology. To sum it up, this paper aims to outline the effects of the different analyses on the potential implementation of the VFR-technology and how this influences online customer

satisfaction and the percentage of returns.

To realize the research objectives and to gain valuable knowledge on the application of VFR-technology, a smaller scope had to be defined. Based on preliminary research and the availability of data, this research is based on a qualitative case-study design and focuses on the 'sports good market' within the larger retail and consumer goods market. Within this specific market, the emphasis lies on the (successful) implementation of these types of technology by leading sports brands. Adidas has been selected in a case-study design as the firm recently started experimenting with VFR-technology in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, and therefore can prove valuable in comparing theory to (business) practice. Data will be retrieved from publicly available sources (e.g. websites, adidas, newspapers), databases, and academic sources such as journals and papers. These sources will add to the knowledge required on VFR-technologies to understand how they can be implemented in the value chain to increase sales and decrease returns. Furthermore, an in-depth interview is conducted with a key account manager from a third-party vendor responsible for the technology of 'profit protection' at adidas. The insights gathered from this interview will be used to compare and emphasize important factors that are beneficial for the effective implementation of VFR-technologies in the Retail sector.

RETAIL AND CONSUMER GOODS

The retail sector is of utmost importance in all OECD (Organisation for Economic and Co-operation and Development) countries. It acts as a gateway to consumers from the supply sectors, accounting for almost 5% of GDP and employing around 1 in 12 people (OECD, 2020). But the global retail market declined from \$21821.4 billion in 2019 to \$21622.6 billion in 2020 (McKinsey & Company, 2019). The offline retail landscape is littered with bankruptcies and continues to be on a downward trajectory. This drop is primarily the consequence of the economic deceleration in countries worldwide as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and the measures taken to contain it (Research and Markets, 2020). However, the online retail sector has expanded enormously. Columbus (2020) states that there has been a 129% year-over-year growth in U.S. & Canadian e-commerce orders as of April and an impressive 146% growth in all online retail orders. Online conversion rates increased with 8.8% in February, a percentage rate which normally represents the level of shopping impulse characteristic of Cyber Mondays (Columbus, 2020). Figure 1 portrays year-on-year growth in weekly online orders in the retail industry during the Coronavirus pandemic in selected countries in Europe in 2020 (Sabanoglu, 2020).

ANALYSIS

In this part, the research paper will outline the different analyses conducted on the VFR-technology and its implications. The IT governance analysis will discuss the change based on the results of the IT-Governance Matrix, which serves as the leading thread through this analysis. The BPI analysis examines the pre and post situation of COVID-19 on both the offline and online shopping experience and discusses the value of the VFR-technology in the value chain. The cybersecurity analysis discusses the types of data, the performed risk assessments, and the possible resilience scenarios. The latter analysis focuses on the potential acceptance of the VFR-technology by customers.

IT governance shift

The sudden acceleration towards increased online shopping by customers has not only revealed cracks in current IT approaches by firms that already existed but also created new ones (Steenhoek, 2020). As the digital transformation progressed, overcoming the well-known challenges in retail in terms of keeping up with altering purchasing patterns and behaviour was not the only issue firms were facing. New concerns emerged during the COVID-19 pandemic that impacted the way retail firms approached their management of IT in order to sustain their competitive advantage and to survive in the changing retail landscape.

The role of IT in the retail industry changed quite dramatically during the lockdown. While at first it was aimed at supporting the physical sales in stores and filling in the gap that was left by the initial closing of stores during the lockdown, it quickly became the cornerstone of many firms as consumers were ordering more products online. After governments (e.g. France, Belgium, Germany) imposed a total ban ongoing outside and visiting physical stores, it became vital that businesses retained their current customer base and ensured their customers' loyalty by engaging with them using online means. While this trend had existed for some time; simplifying online processes, increasing customer satisfaction, and responding to customer demands during the COVID-19 outbreak became indispensable in order for a retail business to survive. The goal was to increase revenues by helping the customer in real-time. Another benefit was that it allowed the retailers to comply with governmental rules that were aimed at minimizing human interaction and increasing hygienic awareness. Retailers (re)structured their organization in combination with dynamic capabilities to be resilient for disruptive events in their external environment. For example, virtual queues were used to limit the number of customers

to be handled simultaneously on their servers (e.g. Ocado in UK, Carrefour in France), or priority delivery was given to vulnerable or elderly customers using timeslots (e.g. Waitrose in the UK). In general, limiting customer access allowed websites to cope with increased traffic and prevent a denial of service from occurring, preventing additional revenue loss. Adequately designed IT systems meant that many firms in the retail sector were able to cope with the increase of online purchases during the COVID-19 outbreak. The role of IT in implementing these changes is indispensable and it is the reason why IT Governance had to be adapted.

According to the interview, the drastic decrease in revenue during the COVID-19 lockdown was one of the main driving forces behind the change of IT-governance policies at adidas. As seen in table 1, decisions in IT at adidas were previously managed mainly on a federal, IT-monarchy, and duopoly level. The management structure of adidas comprised a myriad of layers. Ultimately, C-level leaders were on top of the ladder and were responsible for many decisions within the organization. But initially, a lot of input was requested from the management layers or departments below, which ensured a dynamic composition of responsibilities. This is in line with Adidas' Annual report (2019), in which it is stated that frequent organizational shifts can result in "staff fatigue" and consequently in a reduction in efficiency and productivity. As well, a complex organizational structure and inaccurate division of roles and responsibilities can provoke suboptimal decision-making.

Table 1: adidas' IT Governance matrix pre-COVID-19

Table 2: adidas' IT Governance matrix during-COVID-19

After the initial COVID-19 outbreak, many of the decisions made in IT were now moved upwards towards the C-level in adidas. As the revenues dramatically decreased, this forced the C-level of the company to postpone long-term technological investments. This managerial shift is visible in table 2, in which most decisions are now made by the C-level at adidas in the wake of the COVID-19 outbreak. According to the interview, less input was requested from other management

layers and C-level were executing IT decisions without consulting what other departments requested. This meant that some decisions were made without adequately looking at the requirements from departments, potential costs, and opportunities associated with the implementation of these new systems. C-level executives were so focused on increasing revenues in order to cope with the dynamic COVID-19 environment, that they purchased external tools that they saw being used at other firms and tried to adapt them to adidas. As a result, existing VFR-technology was used and adapted into adidas to support their business model and drive sales. While many other investments were postponed, technologies that increase online customer satisfaction and reduce costs are, however, still invested in by C-level to realize positive net profits after the pandemic is over. As the access to stores remains limited, and awareness of COVID-19 risks means customers are reluctant to visit physical stores, increasing the focus on adequately designed IT-systems that benefit the customer journey, such as VFR technology can prove beneficial in increasing revenues in the long term, long after the COVID-19 pandemic has passed.

Customer journey

Before COVID-19, customers would prefer physical experience, or they would order several colours/sizes of the same items to make sure they had the right one. The percentage of returns of clothes in the fashion industry has always been high compared to other sectors, amounting to approximately \$62 billion annually, while about 70% of them occur because of fit-related problems (Lee & Xu, 2019). Traditionally, around 30-40% of fashion items bought online are returned and since lockdown, returns for some retailers have dropped as low as 5% to 10% (PWC, 2020). This is for a part due to the increased restrictions in returns from the fashion retailers. The second quarter of the year started with a 19% decline in sales for Adidas and for the third quarter, a 34% decrease appeared, after imposed quarantines in many countries. This pandemic will not last forever, and therefore retailers have to think about solutions to stay ahead of the competition and to meet their expectations. While avoiding losing further ground in economic terms.

Adding the Virtual Fitting Room Technology into the current business process of buying an item, may be a solution to tackle the percentage of returns to the future. By virtually translating the physical fitting experiences to the virtual space with the use of sensory elements, VFRs can overcome the inherent problem of online shopping by fulfilling consumers' functional fitting needs as well as providing consumers with an entertaining experience, which is critical for online fashion

consumers (Blazquez, 2014). This idea, of course, has not been invented during the COVID-19 crisis. As the CEO Kasper Rorsted mentioned in an interview with CNBC in early spring, technological solutions are not expected to substitute the physical experience in stores, but rather enhance the e-commerce of the brand nowadays, but also in the years to come (CNBC, 2020). The digital plan however was made in 2017 and yet the transition has seen significant progress during 2020. COVID-19 has unequivocally acted as an accelerator for the business world, making the digital transformation happen faster, like in the case of adidas. adidas' plan to turn "digital" and "analytically oriented" is further implemented with the initiation of various apps (e.g. Runtastic), partnerships with virtual retailers (e.g. Zalando and Alibaba), via virtually alive products. At the same time, following the recent global push for exercise at home, adidas adjusted by promoting "stay-at-home" products (e.g. Adilette Slides, "Face cover" masks) and the use of "#hometeam" in social media for storytelling (Business Insider, 3rd of May 2020). From implementing emotional branding to extensive use of AI and data analytics, we conclude that all enterprises in the retailing industry have been immensely transformed in terms of activities and technology in an effort to improve the supply chain management with advanced distributions in a time-effective way (Business Insider, 3rd of May 2020).

Figure 2: Business Process Diagram based on the pre COVID-19 situation including the physical fitting rooms (see Appendix).

In Figure 2, which is also highlighted in the appendix, the offline shopping experience is displayed with all its several actors involved. The crucial role of the fitting room in the physical experience is visible and the question is how to incorporate it in the online experience and to see what future value it has in terms of satisfaction and eventually in the percentage of returns. Like Kasper Rorsted already mentioned, the importance of physical stores will remain, but technological solutions can enhance the total experience. The management of new technologies and the online channel, as well as its integration in-store for the generation of new experiences, paves the way for establishments that go beyond spaces in which products are acquired (365 Retail, 2018).

Figure 3: Business Process Diagram based on the online purchasing experience including the VFR-technology and an optional sales assistant (see Appendix).

In Figure 3, which is enlarged in the appendix, the VFR-technology is already incorporated in the business process. As previously said, the majority of the online customers often experience fit-related problems, which lead to amongst others an increase in returns. VFR technology has the potential to solve this problem and enhance the total e-commerce experience. Moreover, since the virtual fitting room may have its issues, especially in the beginning, a sales assistant may be needed to assist the customer when needed. This sales assistant can back-up the outcomes of the technology and assist the customer when necessary. Eventually, when the VFR-technology is properly implemented, future research may be needed to prove its relevance in terms of returns and the total customer experience.

Data risks and technology threats

In the corporate world, the rise of cyber-attacks is far outpacing the level of investment in protection from cyber threats: there has been a 33% increase in the cost of cybercrimes since 2016, but investments in cybersecurity lag behind, having only increased by 10% (Brink, 2019). This chapter explains the digital risks associated with Virtual Fitting Room Technology and the business risks of online shopping. Online retail continues to grow, and with a boost in stay-at-home orders as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, it is steadily becoming one of the fastest-growing industries in the world. In tandem with this growth, more data is now being generated. This creates various forms of fraud and risk, which in turn provides opportunities for people with malicious intent to defraud online businesses. For a company like adidas, retrieving, and storing as much data and as many types of data as possible seems a good thing, but brings more problems than benefits (Savitsky, 2019). For example, exposure to the dangers associated with unbridled data collection will lead to a loss of confidence and subsequently to a loss of revenue and lower customer satisfaction (Accenture, 2020). The types of data being collected with the implementation of the VFR technology include amongst other things: biometric data, personal data, location data, digital likeness data, financial data, and electronic data (identification and localization). The collection of this data can conflict with the CIA triangle; confidentiality, integrity and availability. The main

focus here lies on confidentiality and integrity, as biometric data is concerned with the collection of sensitive information such as body measurements and personal information about the person in question. Customers trying on clothes by webcam leaves a trail of data, valuable real-time insights into consumers' wants, and lifestyles for the company in question (Bhattarai, 2020). adidas uses the data mainly for fitting purposes of the individuals and to improve the sizes of adidas in general with the use of smart algorithms. But if adidas can do that, so can competitors, manufacturers, malicious parties, and other unauthorized persons. For the risk assessment analysis on adidas, we made the distinction between potential cyber data risks of the Virtual Fitting Room technology and the potential business risks of online shopping.

Cyber data risks

Since the introduction of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in 2016, the protection of privacy and data has taken a dominant role in the designing of technological features, in order to avoid high-risk hazards when launching a new product such as VFR. VFR's access through personal devices generates great opportunities to be exploited by malicious actors. Personal devices have access to various types of sensitive and personal data (e.g. medical data) while also generate a plethora of metadata through the use of sensors like cameras (e.g. location). Therefore, it is crucial that all risks are examined and analysed as followed.

Starting from the initiation of the app from the user's perspective, personal details such as birthdate, financial data, physical and electronic address will be required for the registration. Continuing the online buying process of the VFR, a user will be expected to "record" himself/herself with his/her device's camera in order for the body measurements to be assessed. Even though images are not explicitly categorized as sensitive (Art. 9 GDPR), they can still reveal sensitive information such as racial or ethnic origin, which requires the controller to ensure an explicit consent from the user before any processing of data can commence. In adidas' case two types of consents need to be asked from the user; one for the use of the app altogether and one where the user agrees to the profiling him/her, for the body measurements to be used to provide tailored recommendations. While consent is undoubtedly vital, the text describing the company's policy regarding the processing of the user's data must be explicit and compliant to the GDPR principles (and other regulations such as the ePrivacy Directive). The content of the regulation should also be presented in such a way that all the information can be read effortlessly while using a mobile (to avoid potential accusations of hiding information in the architectural design). Many cases

have already been to court regarding the neglect of information for certain uses of data by third parties. Privacy and security should therefore be embedded in the system (principle: privacy and security by design). To ensure that VFR complies with multiple privacy regulations, a transparent-visible policy for the user should be implemented. Adidas should therefore hire experts to compose the company's policy (e.g. auditors and legal department).

When dealing with sensitive data, encryption is necessary in order to store the data anonymously. Good security has no trade-offs, which is why choosing efficient encryption algorithms, instead of weaker ones that may be faster to use in the development process, should be chosen. The vulnerabilities from such an algorithm can be detrimental, thus Adidas should have multiple layers of security to ensure end-to-end security. On the other hand, even when using the better-safer choice there are no guarantees. Leaving back-doors open limits the efficiency and gives the opportunity to malicious hackers to exploit them. Encryption standards should be followed. Moreover, another important "detail" that needs attention is the appropriate use of sessions. While the goal of the app and website is to offer the user an uncomplicated and effortless browsing experience, it cannot be overlooked that re-authentication is needed if the user performs multiple actions. Nevertheless, asking for re-authentication too often would be tiresome for the user and because of that developers resort to using tokens. These access tokens must remain confidential and generated once with each access attempt, otherwise an outsider might exploit the information provided in them (ex. their termination should be done immediately after the user terminates the use of the app even if he/she does not log out). In case of a data breach, adidas must report the incident under 72 hours, as stated under GDPR law.

In human-technology interaction, the user will always be the "weakest point" and even though the user cannot be explicitly "trained" for safer use of apps, it is in the company's interest to guide him/her in the right direction. Such guidelines can be achieved by imposed limitations on the type of passwords that can be used. In order to generate stronger passwords on the user's end, practices such as mandatory use of capital letters, numbers and symbols and the inability to try logging in after a specific amount of entering wrong passwords (strong password policies). In addition, we propose using hashes for the user's data, when logging in, and two-type factors for authentication (e.g. OTP), in order to minimize the possibility of "unauthorized access".

Lastly, it is mandatory that the information gathered from the VFR technology is checked using the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). This assessment provides insight in what type of

data is gathered and what is allowed under current privacy regulations. It can furthermore be used to provide insight in the confidentiality, integrity and availability of data, and checks what data is a substantial risk, but not sufficiently covered by the defined user policies. Not conducting a DPIA would be an incredible hazard for adidas as not complying to GDPR law can result in financial penalties. Measures must therefore be in place in case of accidental or intentional loss/ destruction of data.

The proposed measures at hand are of a proactive, and not reactive character. Moreover, a recommendation on behalf of this paper is the measures are based on a specialist attacker and are therefore stricter. The goal is to prevent a data breach, not handling it when it occurs.

Business data risks

In addition to the cybersecurity risks of the data acquired by the VFR technology, online shopping also copes with business risks that affect their annual revenue. As with offline shopping, e-commerce entails various forms of security risks in which customers might commit fraud on the regular online shopping processes. The interview with the industry expert on retail security addressed three major forms of online shopping fraud: friendly fraud, return fraud, and wardrobing. First, friendly fraud refers to the basic premise that a customer has paid for a product which they claim is never delivered or was damaged on delivery. The retailer has to issue a refund, re-deliver the item, or face a chargeback (Columbus, 2020). A second form of online fraud that retailers face is fake returns in which customers return different items than were purchased. For instance, a counterfeit product or stolen item is returned, resulting in a money refund. A third potential form of online fraud that is increasing dramatically in recent years is wardrobing. Customer order products online, wear them for one single occasion and return them afterwards without having paid for them (Shang, Ghosh & Galbreth, 2017).

Retail-fraud appears to be a common phenomenon nowadays which causes a great challenge for retailers as it cannot completely be eliminated. Different forms of fraud are continuously evaluated with new means of committing fraud coming up every year (John, Shah & Kartha, 2020). As retail purchases move online, retail fraud is following this path. The first form of fraud, friendly fraud, occurs intentionally as well as unintentionally and has a really high likelihood (Likelihood score = 4) as often retailers do not want to violate the customer experience of their brand as it is hard to judge whether their customers are right or false in every particular case. The second form of fraud, fake returns, occurs mostly intendedly in

which fraudulent ‘customers’ return other – normally cheaper - products than that were ordered. The likelihood (likelihood score = 3) of this form of fraud is less than the former form of fraud as violation could be judged in the warehouse if different products are returned. For the consumer, the risk of returning different products is higher. Wardrobing as a third form of fraud is fast becoming one of the biggest challenges in the retail industry as no clothes are stolen, but a certain amount of value of the products gets stolen by these fraudulent ‘customers’. Although the likelihood of wardrobing is the biggest for the high-end apparel industry, it is still highly likely in the sports fashion industry (likelihood score = 4).

Based on research conducted by Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (Wells, 2014), it can be concluded that online retail businesses lose 5% of annual revenue because of fraudulent activities. A report from Brightpearl shows that 44% of American retailers agreed that their margins are being strongly impacted by handling and packaging returns. Although the impact is enormous, most retailers nowadays incorporate the probability of fraud within their margins. Therefore, the potential impact can be calculated in advance. From the three forms of fraud, the first two have a higher impact as the original products get ‘stolen’ (Impact score = 2). Additionally, ‘Wardrobers’ pay nothing to use the items they purchase and then typically return a less valuable item to the store. Although the value of the products is decreased and additional logistic costs are needed, retailers normally still sell the product, so the impact is less high (Impact score = 1).

Multiple technologies can be implemented to reduce the chances of different forms of fraud. To reduce the chance of friendly fraud, smart algorithms can be utilized to figure out which transactions are more likely to be fraudulent or not. RFID technology could be an effective technology for the second type of fraud as all products become uniquely identifiable and ‘fake returns’ can be investigated. Lastly, social media analyses can be performed if damaged clothes are returned due to potential wardrobing activities. Another more preventive measurement would be to include a visible tag on the outside of the garment. The visible tag, however, should state that the product cannot be returned after it is subtracted from the product to overcome legal issues. In all measurement cases, however, creating a seamless shopping experience for honest customers seems to be outweighing measurements to reduce fraud from fraudulent customers. A trade-off between security and customer satisfaction has to be made.

Risk assessment matrix

Table 3 is fully elaborated on in the Appendix

and contains the whole risk assessment, but starting with the scenario that adidas’ app will not ask for the two necessary consents from the user, we assess the likelihood to the level 1 (rare), because it is considered common knowledge and therefore it cannot be easily overlooked by the IT developing team.

Table 3. Risk assessment

	Likelihood	Impact	Final score
<i>Cyber security risks</i>			
Lack of consent	1	3	3
Unclear data policy	4	4	16
Identifiable data after decryption	3	5	15
Careless use of tokens	4	1	4
Weak password policy	4	2	8
<i>Business risks</i>			
Friendly fraud	4	2	8
Fake returns	3	2	6
Wardrobing	4	1	4

In terms of *qualitative* approach, this paper deems the 1-5 scale of likelihood to rare→unlikely→ possible→ likely→ certain, while the 1-5 scale of impact to insignificant → minor→ moderate → major → catastrophic.

Firstly, in a scenario in which consent is neglected, there would be a moderate violation to the GDPR resulting in a substantial fine. As the user needs to accept the policy in order to use the app, the likelihood is low. The second scenario implies a situation in which adidas’ company policy is not explicitly explained for the customer, understand, and does not cover all occasions of data use. We assess the risk to be level 4 because it is very likely and also a major violation that would lead to a heavy fine. The third scenario focuses on the identifiability of the data. When dealing with sensitive data it is important that their encryption and separation is done in such a way that should a hacker get access to them he/she would not be able to decrypt the data and identify the customer. We therefore rate it level 3, because it is possible that a company will choose a weaker algorithm to provide a more user-friendly app experience. However, if a hacker is able to identify the data and the user it belongs to, the violation of the GDPR will be once again catastrophic and the fine adjusted accordingly. Moving to the fourth scenario, the use of tokens and

sessions is, as explained before, important for the seamless transition of activities inside the app, but their handling should be careful in order to not give away the user's credentials. Our estimation for its likelihood is at level 4 because it is a likely trap that the app falls into. Yet the impact is found insignificant and is evaluated to 1. Lastly, the fifth scenario about weak password policies that a user is likely to resign for convenience is measured to 4 because people are slowly starting to realize the importance of protecting their data. Its impact is level 2, same as the fourth scenario, because hacking one individual's credentials to the app would be a minor consequence in comparison. Our estimations for the consequences of the cyber risks were done based on some analogy incidents that have occurred recently, as seen in Table 4 in the Appendix.

Managing a business has always been a race against time and "foreseeing" economic change is one of the most desirable abilities. Coping with business risks is not a recent necessity, whereas the value of cybersecurity is only starting to be assessed by the business world. Cybersecurity protects a firm from being undermined when business processes that rely on digital technology fail. The rapid advancement of technology, admittedly, generates constantly newer security risks. Therefore, the management of Cybersecurity is a concern that needs to be addressed by more than the IT departments. It is now crucial that the top-tier management of every business handles cybersecurity risks as well as business risks. Business people need to catch up if they want their business to survive. In conclusion, cyber risks, even though they are still being discovered, are proving to be more significant in the course of business, when it comes to the severity of the repercussions that they may have, in comparison to business risks

Resilience to overcome cybersecurity problems

As cyber incidents become more sophisticated and persistent, companies need to focus on both cybersecurity and cyber-resilience to ensure the protection of their high-risk data. A cyber-resilient company is one that can prevent, detect, contain, and recover from a cyberattack, minimizing exposure time and the impact of countless serious threats against data, applications, and IT infrastructure (Panda, 2018). It is highly important to incorporate reactive and preventive measurements in your resilience strategy after such an attack took place. Minor cybercrime activities that occur frequently should be made preventive and therefore such resilience strategy should be standardized. For the unique and major cybercrime activities, a thorough analysis should be performed in order to see how it happened and what future actions should be considered.

The NIST (The National Institute of Standards and Technology) framework, which was created in 2013, shows a detailed framework, a set of standards and procedures on how to incorporate these risks, but translated into simple language, it would result in the following steps. First, companies should understand their business vulnerabilities. In this step, prioritizing the most valuable assets in a register and tracing back the different threats would be the start of making your company resilient. Secondly, understanding the level of risk within the company is imperative. The company should understand the distribution mechanism, the actors, the potential victims, the attack vectors, TTPs, and the data that is being accessed (Kumar, 2020). As a real-life example, the VFR-technology involves biometric data, and in case of a possible breach, adidas is obliged to publish a public announcement within 72 hours according to the regulation of the GDPR. Lastly, to protect against cyber threats, a company should understand which tools to use and what strategies to implement. The company should incorporate it into the long-term strategy and consider not only the technological factors of cyber-resilience but also the organizational and human factors. It is vital to our economic and societal resilience that we think beyond information security to overall network resilience that ensures we can deal with existing risks and face new risks that will come with such things as artificial intelligence, the internet of things, or quantum computing (Galinec & Steingartner, 2017). This is one of the scenarios adidas can prepare in order to be resilient to such events and it clearly shows that cyber resilience is not only an IT problem but that it is an important part of the risk management process. Eventually, a good-formulated cyber-resilience strategy ensures that a company can effectively countermeasure it, and in the end, ensures protection for all its customers and data.

The consumer perspective

As stated in the introduction, incorporating Virtual Fitting Rooms (VFR) could both stimulate the convenience of customers' online shopping experience as well as reduce their returns. However, the success of this technological application depends upon the usage of the retailers' customers. Customers that undress themselves, so the VFR-technology can assess the body measurements based on pictures, 'undress' themselves as they share sensitive data with the retailer. These sensitive privacy (sharing) customers might not consent with the policy. Therefore, in addition to the analyses on the incorporation of VFR technology into the current business infrastructure from an organizational-perspective, it is important to analyse its impact from a customer-adoption-perspective. If customers are not adopting the technology, the investments do

not deliver their expected return.

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is widely applied within the literature to understand the attitude people hold about the use of technology (Davis, 1989). This model is used to predict the adoption and use of information technology applications by (potential) customers and can be applied to analyse sound predictions of usage by linking behaviours of customers to attitudes and beliefs. To determine the actual system, use of people, several factors should be considered. The adoption of a new technology by people or firms depends both on its perceived ease of use and its perceived usefulness (Davis, 1989). Within this study, perceived usefulness is defined as 'the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance' and perceived ease of use is seen as 'the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort' (Davis, 1989). A combination of these two elements influences the attitude of people towards using the information system application, which finally influences the behavioural intention to use it.

For adidas, in order to realize an increase in sales and a decrease in returns, this theory indicates that the VFR technology should be incorporated within their e-commerce channels to achieve usefulness as well as ease of use for their customers. Currently, fitting clothes via virtual reality using your own avatar on your mobile phone is still not common practice for customers (Business Insider US, 2020). An important question, therefore, is why the additional effort of an VFR for customers outweighs the current option to order multiple sizes and return the sizes that do not fit. As one of the early adopters of the technology, adidas should make their customers aware of the usefulness of the VFR application and, additionally, make it as easy as possible for customers to use it. Specific online and offline marketing campaigns could help to realize this. Complementary research of Wixom and Todd (2005) have mentioned the supplementary effects of trialability, compatibility, and result demonstrability to affect the attitude toward usage. When it is compatible with the existing e-commerce procedure and the application is easy triable, the attitude of customers towards usage can be influenced by adidas. Additionally, by demonstrating positive usages of VFR by people in which customers can identify themselves influences the attitude of potential customers towards usage. Lastly, with an increased awareness of customers on sustainability, adidas could utilize the added value of VFR towards customers as less returns reduces the social and environmental impacts through reduced transport and handling (de Leeuw et al., 2016).

Figure 4. Model retrieved from Wixom and Todd (2005) extending the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989) by the user satisfaction research approach.

Based on Technology Acceptance Model of Davis (1989), Wixom and Todd (2005) have conducted a study to build the theoretical logic that links the user satisfaction with the technology acceptance literature and concluded that Information satisfaction and system satisfaction are the key enablers influencing the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use within the adoption of information systems. As can be found in Figure 3, completeness, format, currency, and accuracy of the information from VFR for customers are the antecedents indirectly influencing the information satisfaction via information quality. Reliability, integration, accessibility, and flexibility of the information from VFR for customers are the antecedents indirectly influencing system satisfaction via system quality. Therefore, before launching the FVR application, adidas should acknowledge and improve the antecedents influencing information satisfaction and system satisfaction. Doing so has a double-sided effect as it might positively influence customers' behavioural beliefs, attitudes, and intentions to try the application, as well as reuse the application if it worked out well. When the application proves itself to be useful in terms of the right sizes as well as easy in terms of less effort than returning items, the 'chance that customers will accept the technology as 'the new normal of ecommerce' will increase.

Lee and Xu (2020) classified different VFR technologies on their impact on customer experience based on 20 different use cases. They concluded that applying technologies like Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality and full 3D body scans come with the trade-off between accuracy and attractiveness. Therefore, as adidas has a wide scope of products, this classification can be used to use the appropriate VFR-technology for shoes as well as clothes.

DISCUSSION

For the sports fashion retail industry, the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic has a massive impact on the business of retailers. Online shopping behaviour has increased and as a result the number of returns has increased as well having an impact on the (operational) costs of retailers due to logistics as well as depreciation of clothes. Additionally, the IT Governance analysis has revealed that the Governance within adidas has changed due to the

pandemic. Instead of a federal and bureaucratic decision-making design, the Business Monarchy decides on nearly all strategic aspects. As has been mentioned during the interview, within adidas, the revenues have dramatically decreased which forced the C-level of the company to postpone long-term technological investments. Technologies that increase online customer satisfaction and reduce costs are, however, invested in by C-level to realize positive net profits after the Pandemic is over. The VFR-technology could be one of the technologies to fulfil this demand and, therefore, be implemented by the C-level of adidas.

Although a positive business case of the investment can be expected as costs will be reduced and sales are expected to be increased, too quickly implementing this technology by C-level without incorporating IT might have negative drawbacks. As investigated in the Risk Assessment analysis, however, the costs could be dramatically bigger if cybersecurity risks are not considered. Therefore, it is extremely important to use the knowledge retrieved by this analysis to undertake preventive as well as prepare reactive measurements to reduce the impact of the risks finally. Therefore, this study implies that quick strategic IT responses by C-level management on the impact of external crises could positively influence the net profits for the short run, while attracting risk for the long run performance of the company. Hence, Virtual Fitting Room Technology could be a possible vaccine for the COVID-19 Virus in Retail to overcome the challenges on e-commerce that arose due to the global pandemic. However, as with the extensive development of normal vaccines that should avoid long-term consequences on people's health, extensive research and development is needed into the implementation of VFR technology, so the technology adds value to the customers and avoids potential (future) risks on Cybersecurity.

Within the eyewear industry, for instance, VFR-technology has been adopted by retailers for some years with a clear strategy on the possible risks of cybersecurity involved. The Dutch firm Specsavers uses augmented reality in their VFR-technology to determine the size of your glasses and the fit with your head. While processing the scans of your face, you can see the steps they do with your biometric data, so you know how your data is being processed. In the data policy, which has to be accepted by means of a consent, it is stated that they keep the biometric information only for 30 days. The sports fashion industry could learn from these related industries to overcome IT-related problems and risks.

CONCLUSION

Virtual Fitting Room Technology has the potential to be a vaccine for the COVID-19 Virus in the Retail sector. However, as previous research has shown, new technologies come hand in hand with hidden risks that have to be examined. Research, based on an adidas case study, has shown that the VFR-technology can fill the existing gaps within online shopping. The decision-making process within companies such as adidas has shifted to a more C-level archetype, in which other departments have few inputs. Therefore, companies must carefully consider new technologies, such as VFR-technology to ensure a successful implementation. Research has also shown that there is a potential for the VFR-technology in the purchasing process, but this needs to be well supported by back-office activities to support proper implementation. With all the data collected by the technology, both consciously and unconsciously, it is crucial to stay ahead of the potential risks that may arise. To ensure that the cyber data is handled properly, it is crucial to comply with all elements of the GDPR and to include them systematically in the policy. Furthermore, the risk assessment matrix shows qualitative results that explain the possible impacts of possible risks. For a company such as adidas, it is therefore important to include a good-formulated cyber-resilience strategy in the company's strategy. Although this research is based on the apparel retail sector, and specifically adidas, it is market-wide applicable.

Research suggestions

Based on this research, several further research suggestions can be made. As stated in analysis 4.4, further research is needed to determine which VFR-technologies of Lee and Xu (2020) are appropriate for adidas for all their product categories. This study should focus both on the adoption and risks from a business-perspective as well as customer-perspective. A focus should be on machine learning and the opportunity of artificial intelligence.

Next to that, a multiple case study design should be used to investigate the antecedents of a digital transformation process of retailers implementing VFR-technology. This study could incorporate the combination with offline Virtual Fitting Room technology as well, so the technology can be combined for retailers' customers in their omnichannel experience. Lastly, a more extensive study should be done into the cybersecurity risks that are applicable to the sensitive data that arise from the VFR-technology.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank Kevin for his contribution to the project as he gave us very valuable insights into the governance processes within adidas from before and after the COVID-19 pandemic during the conducted interview. Furthermore, for this research we really appreciate the effort of the professors to organize a project that incorporates all three courses in an offline bootcamp.

REFERENCES

- Accenture. (2020). *COVID-19: Consumers change how they shop, work and live*. <https://www.accenture.com/tr-en/insights/retail/coronavirus-consumer-behavior-research>
- Accenture the Netherlands. (2020). *The risks of unbridled data collection* | Accenture Insights. WordPressBlog. <https://www.accenture.com/nl-en/blogs/insights/less-is-more-the-risks-of-unbridled-data-collection>
- adidas Group. (2020). Annual Report 2019. nexxar GmbH, Vienna. <https://report.adidas-group.com/2019/en/group-management-report-our-company/corporate-strategy.html#accordion7>
- Bhattacharai, A. (2020). *Virtual try-ons are replacing fitting rooms during the pandemic*. Washington Post. https://www.washingtonpost.com/gdpr-consent/?next_url=https%3a%2f%2fwww.washingtonpost.com%2fbusiness%2f2020%2f07%2f09%2fvirtual-try-ons-are-replacing-fitting-rooms-during-pandemic%2f
- Blazquez, M. (2014). Fashion shopping in multichannel retail: The role of technology in enhancing the customer experience. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 18(4), 97–116.
- Business Insider US. (2020). *Retailers like Macy's, Adidas, and Modcloth are turning to virtual fitting rooms to let consumers "try on" clothing before buying it online*. Business Insider Nederland. <https://www.businessinsider.nl/retailers-like-macys-adidas-are-turning-to-virtual-fitting-rooms-2020-8?international=true&r=US>
- Clark, T. (2018, 29 juni). The physical shopping experience: 3 trends that build customer loyalty. 365 RETAIL | eCommerce and Social Retail news and updates. <https://www.365retail.co.uk/the-physical-shopping-experience-3-trends-that-build-customer-loyalty/>
- CNCB, (2020) *Adidas CEO: We are a very hot brand in China, not seeing slowdown*. (2019, 3 mei). [Video]. CNBC. <https://www.cnbc.com/video/2019/05/03/adidas-ceo-we-are-a-very-hot-brand-in-china-not-seeing-slowdown.html>
- CNCB, (2020) *Adidas CEO Kasper Rorsted: 70% of our stores closed down*. (2020, 27 april). [Video]. CNBC. <https://www.cnbc.com/video/2020/04/27/adidas-ceo-kasper-rorsted-70percent-of-our-stores-closed-down.html>
- Columbus, L. (2020). *How COVID-19 Is Transforming E-Commerce*. Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/louiscolumbus/2020/04/28/how-covid-19-is-transforming-e-commerce/#9d932913544f>
- Columbus, L. (2020). *How E-Commerce's Explosive Growth Is Attracting Fraud*. Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/louiscolumbus/2020/05/18/how-e-commerces-explosive-growth-is-attracting-fraud/#64a4aa3d6c4b>
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS quarterly*, 319–340.
- De Leeuw, S., Minguela-Rata, B., Sabet, E., Boter, J., & Sigurðardóttir, R. (2016). Trade-offs in managing commercial consumer returns for online apparel retail. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*.
- Galinec, D., & Steingartner, W. (2017). Combining cybersecurity and cyber defense to achieve cyber resilience. *2017 IEEE 14th International Scientific Conference on Informatics*. doi:10.1109/informatics.2017.8327227
- Hjort, K., & Lantz, B. (2016). The impact of returns policies on profitability: A fashion e-commerce case. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(11), 4980–4985.
- Ingilizian, Z. (2020). *How the coronavirus is boosting the stay-at-home economy*. World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/05/covid19-coronavirus-digital-economy-consumption-e-commerce-stay-at-home-online-education-streaming/>
- John, S., Shah, B. J., & Kartha, P. (2020). Refund fraud analytics for an online retail purchases. *Journal of Business Analytics*, 1–11.
- Kumar, S.U. (2020). Cyber Resilience: A New Way of Looking at Cybersecurity. Website: <https://www.securitymagazine.com/articles/92456-cyber-resilience-a-new-way-of-looking-at-cybersecurity>
- Lee, H., & Xu, Y. (2020). Classification of virtual fitting room technologies in the fashion industry: from the perspective of consumer

- experience. *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education*, 13(1), 1-10.
- McKinsey & Company. (2019). *Perspectives on retail and consumer goods* (Nr. 7). © 2019 McKinsey & Company.
https://www.mckinsey.com/~media/McKinsey/Industries/Retail/Our%20Insights/Perspectives%20on%20retail%20and%20consumer%20goods%20Number%207/Perspectives-on-Retail-and-Consumer-Goods_Issue-7.ashx
- O.E.C.D. (2020). *COVID-19 and the retail sector: impact and policy responses*. OECD.
<http://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/covid-19-and-the-retail-sector-impact-and-policy-responses-371d7599/>
- Pachoulakis, I., & Kapetanakis, K. (2012). Augmented Reality Platforms for Virtual Fitting Rooms. *The International journal of Multimedia & Its Applications*, 4(4), 35–46.
<https://doi.org/10.5121/ijma.2012.4404>
- Panda Security (2018). How to make your company cyber resilient? Website:
<https://www.pandasecurity.com/mediacenter/news/cyber-resilience-report/>
- Piotrowicz, W., & Cuthbertson, R. (2014). Introduction to the Special Issue Information Technology in Retail: Toward Omnichannel Retailing. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 18(4), 5–16.
<https://doi.org/10.2753/jec1086-4415180400>
- PWC (2020): How fashion retailers can tackle a possible surge in returns.
<https://www.pwc.co.uk/issues/crisis-and-resilience/covid-19/how-fashion-retailers-can-tackle-the-plunge-in-return-rates.html>
- Research and Markets. (2020). *Global Retail Market Report (2020 to 2030) - COVID-19 Impact and Recovery*. © 2020 GlobeNewswire, Inc. All Rights Reserved.
<https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2020/05/14/2033483/0/en/Global-Retail-Market-Report-2020-to-2030-COVID-19-Impact-and-Recovery.html#:~:text=The%20global%20retail%20market%20is,the%20measures%20to%20contain%20it.>
- Sabanoglu, T. (2020). *Weekly order trends in online retail during Covid-19 in Europe 2020*. Statista.
<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1109296/online-retail-y-o-y-order-trends-during-coronavirus-in-europe/>
- Savitsky, A. (2019). The Dangers of Having Too Much Data. Kaspersky official blog.
<https://www.kaspersky.com/blog/too-much-data/5144/>
- Shang, G., Ghosh, B. P., & Galbreth, M. R. (2017). Optimal retail return policies with wardrobing. *Production and Operations Management*, 26(7), 1315-1332.
- Smart insights. (2020) *Convenience is driving e-commerce growth and influencing consumer decisions*.
<https://www.smartinsights.com/ecommerce/customer-experience-examples/convenience-is-driving-e-commerce-growth-and-influencing-consumer-decisions/>
- Steenhoek, B. (2020). Retail's digital future: challenges and opportunities in the post-covid-19 world. Atos. <https://atos.net/en/blog/retails-digital-future-challenges-and-opportunities-in-the-post-covid-19-world>
- Wells, J. T. (2014). Report to the nation on occupational fraud and abuse. Association of Certified Fraud Examiner. Retrieved from Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (ACFE) website <https://www.acfe.com/rtnn/docs/2014-report-to-nations.pdf>
- Wixom, B. H., & Todd, P. A. (2005). A theoretical integration of user satisfaction and technology acceptance. *Information systems research*, 16(1), 85-102.
- Yang, S., & Xiong, G. (2019). Try It On! Contingency Effects of Virtual Fitting Rooms. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 36(3), 789-822.

APPENDIX

Table 1: adidas' IT Governance matrix pre-COVID-19

IT Activities (Input/Decision)	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Archetype										
Business Monarchy										
IT Monarchy				x		x				
Feudal			x		x				x	
Federal		x					x	x		x
IT Duopoly	x									
Anarchy										

Table 2: adidas' IT Governance matrix during-COVID-19

IT Activities (Input/Decision)	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Archetype										
Business Monarchy		x		x		x				x
IT Monarchy										
Feudal							x			
Federal	x		x		x			x	x	
IT Duopoly										
Anarchy										

Figure 2: Business Process Diagram based on the pre COVID-19 situation including the physical fitting rooms.

Figure 3: Business Process Diagram based on the online purchasing experience including the VFR-technology and an optional sales assistant.

Table 3: risk assessment matrix

Form of Risk	Cybersecurity risks								Business risks
Scenario	1.Lack of consent	2.Unclear policy data	3.Identifiable data after decryption	4.Careless use of tokens/sessions	5.Weak password policy	6.Friendly fraud	7.Fake returns	8.Wardrobing	
Likelihood	1	4	3	4	4	4	3	4	
Impact	3	4	5	1	2	2	2	1	
Final score	3	16	15	4	8	8	6	4	
Risk rank	6	1	2	5	3	3	4	5	
Measurement	Asking for consent of users (preventive)	Policy in line with GDPR and use of experts (auditors and lawyers) (preventive)	Within 72 hours public announcement (reactive) Follow encryption standards (preventive)	Within 72 announcement to user (reactive) Termination standards (preventive)	Standard strong password policies (preventive)	Smart algorithms (preventive)	RFID technology (reactive)	Social media analyses (reactive) Visible tags (preventive)	
Effectivity of measurement	high	medium	medium	high	high	medium	high	low / high	

Table 4: analogy incidents that help evaluate the risks determined in Table 3 in terms of impact

Country	Date	Fine (€)	Controller/Processor	Risk Relation	Authority
Germany	2020-10-01	35,258,708	H&M Hennes & Mauritz Online Shop A.B. & Co. KG	No consent	Data Protection Authority of Hamburg
United Kingdom	2019-07-08	204,600,000	British Airways	Identifiable data	Information Commissioner (ICO)
France	2019-01-21	50,000,000	Google Inc.	Unclear data policy	French Data Protection Authority (CNIL)
Germany	2019-12-09	9,550,000	Telecoms provider (1&1 Telecom GmbH)	Weak password policy	The Federal Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information (BfDI)
Poland	2019-09-10	645,000	Morele.net	Insufficient organisational and technical safeguards→ tokens/sessions	Polish National Personal Data Protection Office (UODO)